

MIND MEETS MACHINE: REVOLUTIONIZING MENTAL HEALTH WITH CHATBOTS AND DIGITAL PHENOTYPING

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted an urgent need for scalable mental health solutions, leading to the rise of chatbots and digital phenotyping as innovative interventions. This study examines how intelligent chatbots like Ethika leverage digital phenotyping to provide personalized mental health support by analyzing user data such as screen time and app usage. These systems address mental health disparities, particularly in underserved areas, by offering accessible, real-time recommendations and resources. Despite their potential, ethical concerns regarding data privacy remain critical for building trust in these technologies. This research underscores the transformative potential of chatbots in advancing remote mental health care while emphasizing the need for ethical safeguards.

Keywords: Mental Health, Chatbots, Digital Phenotyping, Covid-19, Personalized Care

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INTRODUCTION

As the COVID-19 pandemic progressed and eventually subsided, it amplified the mental health crisis to unprecedented levels. A systematic review was conducted, showing the pandemic's profound psychological impact on the general population, reaching medically concerning levels: stress surged from 8.1% pre-pandemic to 81.9% afterward, anxiety increased from 6.33% to 50.9%, and depression rose from 14.6% to 48.3% (Xiong et al. 2020). More than half of American adults experienced a mental health illness in their lifetime due to the pandemic's effects (Sepahpour 2020). Amidst challenges like global lockdowns and quarantines, there was a rapid adoption of telehealth as a virtually accessible treatment method (Wosik, et al. 2020). This shift exemplified a critical need for scalable and cost-effective health interventions, leading to the emergence of mental health chatbots as innovative alternatives to traditional therapy.

Chatbots are advanced technologies that engage individuals who may hesitate to seek help due to stigma or lack of access to adequate facilities and resources. In 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) highlighted the severe shortage of mental health services resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic (Khawaja & Bélisle-Pipon 2023). Consequently, the U.S. would require 4 million more health professionals in psychology to treat everyone with mental health conditions (Torous et al. 2021). However, chatbots hold promise in addressing this deficit, particularly in underserved rural and remote areas (Khawaja & Bélisle-Pipon 2023). These virtual assistants offer personalized responses, suggesting physical exercises, mindfulness practices, and coping strategies while providing information on mental health conditions and treatments or directing users to healthcare professionals if needed (Haque & Rubya 2023).

Ethika, an intelligent chatbot will use digital phenotyping to analyze user data and deliver mental health recommendations. This method employs various sources, including screen time and app usage to create a comprehensive profile of an individual's digital phenotype (Coghlan & D'Alfonso 2021). By analyzing patterns and trends in user interactions with technology, chatbots can detect changes in mood, behavior, and cognitive function (Prakash, et al. 2021). However, it is crucial to address ethical concerns regarding data privacy in digital phenotyping to ensure trust and efficacy in mental health care (Oudin, et al. 2023). Therefore, integrating digital phenotyping into chatbot functionalities not only enhances user engagement but also advances the capability to provide proactive and individualized mental health support remotely.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tele-Health In Mental Health (Telemental Health)

As mentioned previously, the rapid adoption and development of telehealth were accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which compelled healthcare providers to innovate and find new solutions. As the healthcare system transitioned from a fee-for-service model to one that reimburses medical professionals based on patient outcomes and quality, telehealth has accommodated these changes while still providing necessary care. Telehealth benefits not only hospitals and healthcare providers by streamlining operations but also reduces costs and time for patients, enhancing accessibility to mental health care for individuals in rural areas (Bulkes et al. 2022). Furthermore, telehealth includes many practices and specialties, incorporating communication between patients and physicians via phone, email, video calls, messaging, the Internet, and remote devices (Gajarawala and Pelkowski 2020). A 2020 study by the American Psychological Association demonstrated that 75% of clinicians surveyed provided remote services, such as therapy via phone or videoconference, and felt confident in their methods (Molfenter et al. 2021).

Digital Phenotyping

Digital phenotyping is defined as a specialized field of science that studies how various technologies—including digital devices like smartphones, social media platforms, and other electronic tools—impact human health and behavior (Smith et al. 2023). This field explores digital activity and can provide insights into individuals' well-being and psychological states. Building on this definition, digital phenotyping can be applied in a clinical context to enhance mental health care (Oudin et al. 2023). They explain that by utilizing digital phenotyping, a chatbot can develop an individualized understanding of users (Oudin et al. 2023). This is achieved by analyzing a range of observable and measurable traits and behaviors derived from users' digital habits. Through this approach, the chatbot can offer real-time quantification of users' experiences, allowing for more precise and timely assessments of their mental health (Oudin et al. 2023).

Active and Passive Data

Active data, called ecological momentary assessments, involves surveys and questionnaires that prompt individual responses (Coghlan & D'Alfonso 2021). In contrast, passive data tracks a person's activity indirectly through sensors without their awareness, potentially reducing bias and providing raw, accurate results (Coghlan & D'Alfonso 2021). For example, a recent study on schizophrenia analyzed both active data, which included self-reported information, and passive data, which tracked behavioral features like sleep, mobility, conversations, and smartphone use (Bufano et al. 2023). On one hand, active data is purely subjective and introduces the challenge of keeping users engaged during surveys and questionnaires, however, passive data automatically collects information using sensors and logs, remaining completely objective (Onnela 2020). However, there are concerns with data privacy for both methods.

Data Privacy

As digital phenotyping requires further research investigation, it involves the collection of immense amounts of individual digital data and categorizing them based on health and risk assessment (Martinez-Martin 2018). Chatbots in particular raise major concerns about data privacy because they not only interact with the user's information, they also learn and adapt to the algorithm on their own. Additionally, most users do not know when or how their personal information is shared or stored (Hasal et al. 2021). Interacting with chatbots carries the risk of inadvertently exposing sensitive information, such as personal health records or business secrets, which could lead to data breaches and compromise privacy and confidentiality, requiring careful integration into systems handling Protected Health Information (PHI) and strict compliance with data protection regulations (Banerjee et al. 2023).

Mental Health Chatbots

Chatbots are systems capable of engaging in conversation and interaction with human users through spoken, written, and visual language (Denecke et al. 2020). They have many advantages with their utilization such as a reduction in the stigma associated with sharing symptoms of mental illness with physicians, increasing personal comfort with self-disclosure, cost-effectiveness, and broadening accessibility, however, while possessing a varied skill set, lack of emotional awareness and empathetic responses of human psychiatrists or therapists (Pham et al. 2022). Nevertheless, they enable users to comfortably share depressive symptoms with virtual counselors ensuring anonymity and privacy, thus eliminating the fear of judgment (Chin et al. 2023). Compared to discussing issues with friends, family, or therapists, interacting with virtual agents is less daunting and these systems have continuous availability, offering immediate and convenient assistance without the need for appointments (Chin et al. 2023).

JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) File

JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a text-based format used for storing and exchanging data that is both human-readable and simple for machines to interpret (Erickson 2024). Its clear structure makes JSON straightforward to learn and simple to troubleshoot, enabling both beginners and experienced developers to work with it efficiently (Erickson 2024). While it originated from JavaScript, JSON has evolved into a versatile format that allows for effortless data interchange across various platforms and programming languages (Erickson 2024). It organizes data into key-value pairs and arrays, which can be accessed by the software that utilizes it (Ozanich 2024). JSON enables developers to store diverse data types in a format that is easy for humans to read, with keys acting as identifiers and values containing the associated information (Ozanich 2024).

Application Programming Interface (API) Key

An API key is a unique code to identify and authenticate applications or users, providing security as an identifier and confidential credential. They manage software interactions, handling requests and data formats, and are widely used in applications and websites for data access and individual interactions. API keys enhance developer flexibility by allowing custom access control, integration between other APIs, and performance testing before deployment (Pulsifer 2023). They also improve security by authentication, tracking usage, and detecting malicious activity (Pulsifer 2023). Overall, API keys offer a versatile solution for managing, securing, and optimizing application access and data exchange, supporting efficiency and innovation (Pulsifer 2023).

The Effects of Social Media and Messaging on Mental Health

Social media is used for entertainment, and education, and can even be someone's job. It is a large umbrella that includes websites and online tools that allow interactions between users by providing them with opportunities to share information, opinions, and interests (Ostic et al. 2021). People, especially adolescents and young adults rely greatly on social media to determine their psychological well-being. The Displaced Behavior Theory may explain the cause of this relationship; people who spend more time by themselves (such as scrolling on social media) have less time for real-life social interaction which has proven to deteriorate their mental state (Karim et al. 2020). The main feature responsible for this is chatting on social media because of constant messaging with other people without the feeling of their physician's presence and cyberbullying, as private chat rooms are not supervised (Beyari 2023). Additionally, browsing posts and advertisements often promote false and materialistic ideals which result in people, especially the younger audience, comparing themselves to these impossible standards, leading to insecurity and possible mental disorders (Beyari 2023).

The Impact of Gaming on Mental Health

Playing video games to the extent that it is considered an "addiction" can result in unhealthy habits and lifestyles. For example, excessive gaming has been found to result in low self-esteem, productivity in doing necessary tasks, anxiety, aggression, and depression (Heiden et al. 2019). Many adults and teenagers seek video games in their free time to distract themselves from larger problems, cope and escape from reality, avoid social interaction, or even have personal satisfaction and competition (Heiden et al. 2019). All of these effects from video gaming could potentially affect the user's behavior and how they treat others such as loss of relationships and connection with their family and friends, lower levels of interest and engagement in school, work, hobbies, and passions which could lead to poor performance in these areas (Li et al. 2022). Despite the negative outcomes, gaming, when done in moderation, can improve cognition, focus, multitasking, goal achievement, memory, visual attention, and emotional regulation, while also reducing stress and anxiety (Kowal et al. 2021).

The Gap

Current research offers valuable insights into emotional recognition, telemental health, and the effects of screen use on mental health. However, there is a notable gap in understanding how these elements intersect with digital phenotypes and chatbot interactions. Specifically, limited exploration has been conducted on how patterns of app usage and screen time are integrated into digital phenotypes and how these factors impact the accuracy and effectiveness of chatbot responses. The relationship between different types of app engagement, the duration of screen time, and their representation in digital systems remains underexplored.

This raises a crucial question: How can chatbots utilize digital phenotyping data to help users manage their mental health?

METHODOLOGY

This paper employs an experimental methodology to bridge the knowledge gap regarding digital phenotyping and chatbots in advancing mental health care. The method includes the data collected and analyzed by the chatbot while addressing the ethical implications inherent to this approach. The primary objective is to validate how these technologies can enhance mental health management and treatment, particularly in the post-pandemic landscape, and to understand how chatbots can effectively utilize digital phenotyping data to support users in managing their mental health.

RESEARCH PROCESS

Figure 1: Phase 1 of the research process as a flowchart

The process began with a comprehensive review of various types of chatbots, including linguistic-based, keyword recognition, machine learning, and voice bots (Lisowski 2023). After evaluating these options, it was determined that to meet the objectives, a chatbot capable of either drawing information from a reliable, pre-existing source or allowing customization with specific data was required.

Two effective methods for achieving this were identified: using a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file for custom data input or integrating an Application Programming Interface (API) key for data retrieval. However, due to the limited availability of reliable sources for API integration, a suitable external data source could not be identified. Opting for the JSON file approach, responses were made based on thorough research to ensure the chatbot delivers relevant and accurate interactions (refer to Figure 1).

Phase 2: What data will be necessary in the JSON file?

Figure 2: Data (questions and corresponding questions) necessary for the JSON file that will code Ethika

The next phase of the research process focuses on developing the content to be incorporated into the chatbot, specifically for customizing responses stored in the JSON file. The process began with outlining the key questions the chatbot needs to address during user interactions (refer to Figure 2). Based on this outline, a range of potential responses was crafted to match various user inputs. To ensure the responses were informative and relevant, extensive research was conducted to understand the underlying causes and contexts for each possible user question. This research aimed to provide accurate and meaningful answers, enhancing the chatbot's ability to deliver proven and useful information.

Different scenarios and user responses were carefully considered to create a comprehensive set of replies that effectively address user needs and ensure the chatbot's interactions are engaging and informative.

DEVELOPMENT LANGUAGE AND PLATFORM

The platform used to code Ethika (see Appendix A) is called Replit. It's an excellent coding platform for both beginners and experienced developers due to its user-friendly interface and vast set of features. It offers a cloud-based environment that allows users to write, test, and deploy code in various programming languages without setting up complex local development settings. Its collaborative features are useful for team projects, enabling multiple users to work on the same codebase simultaneously. Replit's built-in support for version control, live previews, and easy integration with other tools makes it an ideal platform for developing and refining code efficiently.

Python is an excellent choice for coding a chatbot due to its simplicity, readability, and extensive libraries that facilitate natural language processing and machine learning. Its straightforward syntax allows developers to write and understand code quickly, which is crucial for building and refining complex chatbot functionalities. Python's rich ecosystem includes libraries for natural language processing and machine learning, which help create intelligent and responsive chatbots. Additionally, Python's support for conditional logic through 'if-else' statements enables developers to implement decision-making processes and handle various user inputs effectively. These statements allow the chatbot to execute different actions based on specific conditions, providing tailored responses and improving the overall user experience.

The code utilized 'if-else' statements to guide Ethika's actions based on user input, enabling it to respond appropriately to various scenarios and enhancing its adaptability.

```
if best_match:
    answer: str | None = get_answer_for_question(best_match, knowledge_base)
    print(f'Ethika: {answer}')
else:
    print("Ethika: I don't have an answer for that question. Can you teach me?")
    new_answer: str = input('Type the answer or "skip" to skip: ')

    if new_answer.lower() != 'skip':
        knowledge_base["questions"].append({"question": user_input, "answer": new_answer})
        save_knowledge_base(knowledge_base_file, knowledge_base)
        print('Ethika: Thank you for teaching me!')
    else:
        print('Ethika: Okay, no problem.')
```

Figure 3: Using 'if-else' statements in Ethika's code, the chatbot understands what to do based on user inputs.

For instance, as illustrated in Figure 3, Ethika is programmed to retrieve an answer (via 'get_answer_for_question') by finding the best match ('best_match') from the JSON file (referred to as 'knowledge_base'). If a match is found, Ethika responds with 'Ethika: ' followed by the answer; if not, it defaults to the 'else' clause and prints "Ethika: I don't have an answer..." as shown in the figure. Subsequently, the chatbot prompts the user to teach it the correct response or type 'skip'. If the user chooses to teach Ethika, the input and output are saved to the JSON file, and Ethika responds with 'Ethika: Thank you for teaching me!'. If the user types 'skip', Ethika replies with 'Ethika: Okay, no problem.' and offers the user another chance to type another input.

'If-else' statements were also used to establish a threshold, determining Ethika's actions based on whether the numerical input provided was above, below, or met this threshold. This approach allowed Ethika to respond appropriately to different inputs by executing specific actions or delivering tailored responses depending on where the input fell about the set threshold.

```

threshold = 120
user_number = float(user_input)
if user_number > threshold:
    print('Ethika: Your screen time is higher than '
          'the recommended amount by the FDA (2 hours '
          'or less not counting work hours). Do you use '
          'your device in the first hour when you wake '
          'up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?')
elif user_number == threshold:
    print('Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is exactly '
          'the recommended amount (2 hours or less not counting '
          'work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour '
          'when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?')
else:
    print('Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is less than the '
          'recommended amount (2 hours or less not counting work hours). '
          'Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in '
          'the morning/the hour before you go to bed?')

```

Figure 4: The threshold specified in the code allows Ethika to determine and curate its output by using 'if-else' statements, adjusting its responses based on whether the input exceeds or falls short of the threshold value.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the chatbot employs a threshold to guide its responses based on whether the user input falls above, below or matches this threshold, managed through 'if-else' statements. For instance, if the user's screen time is below 120 minutes (two hours), Ethika congratulates them. Conversely, if the screen time exceeds this limit, Ethika provides information supported by FDA guidelines. The 'elif' clause, short for 'else if,' facilitates this process by allowing Ethika to evaluate multiple conditions within a single coding block. This ensures that Ethika can accurately determine whether the input meets, exceeds, or falls short of the threshold, and then delivers responses aligned with FDA recommendations.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

As this paper was experimental, hypothetical responses were entered into Ethika based on yes/no questions or numerical inputs, which were not derived from pre-existing data sources or human subjects. However, the chatbot will store data from previous yet anonymous participants with a possibility of accidental leakage and malfunctioning. Bringing chatbots like Ethika into mental health care is promising but brings several ethical considerations to the forefront. First, is the issue of data privacy. Given that chatbots will process and store sensitive personal information, including potentially identifiable data related to mental health, there is a significant risk of data breaches or unauthorized access. Ensuring encryption methods, strict access

controls and compliance with data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) is imperative to safeguard user information. The GDPR is a law that establishes guidelines for the collection and processing of personal information from individuals both within and outside the European Union. Meanwhile HIPAA applies to the United States and is aimed at reforming the health insurance industry to protect patients' "Protected Health Information" (PHI). Despite these laws, the risk of accidental leakage cannot be eliminated, and maintaining user trust through transparency about data handling practices is crucial.

Furthermore, informed consent is a critical aspect of deploying chatbots in mental health care. Users must be informed about how their data will be used, stored, and shared, as well as the limitations and capabilities of the chatbot. This requires transparent communication about the nature of interactions with the chatbot and obtaining explicit consent before engaging in data collection. Ensuring that users have a clear understanding of their rights and the potential risks involved is essential for ethical practice. Hence, Ethika provides a disclaimer, warning the users not to share personal and sensitive information (see Figure 5).

Another ethical concern involves the accuracy and reliability of the chatbot's responses. Inaccurate or inappropriate advice could lead to harmful outcomes, particularly in mental health scenarios where users may be vulnerable. Therefore, continuous monitoring, validation, and updating of the chatbot's algorithms and responses are essential to minimize the risk of delivering misleading or potentially dangerous recommendations. Additionally, the limitations of robots in understanding complex human emotions and context must be acknowledged, as over-reliance on such systems might inadvertently lead to inadequate care or misinterpretation of user needs. Due to this, Ethika warns the user to be aware that she is not and cannot replace a medical professional (refer to Figure 5). The purpose of Ethika is to guide the user to improve their mental health, not confirm or provide a diagnosis.

```
print('Hello! I'm Ethika, here to help analyze your digital data. '
      'What is your average screen time per day? (Please provide '
      'the number of minutes without using the word "minutes" in your '
      'answer.) Disclaimer: I am not a medical professional. Please do not '
      'share any sensitive information.')
```

Figure 5: Ethika provides a disclaimer, making sure users know her limitations.

RESULTS

The process began with a review of various chatbot types, such as linguistic-based, keyword recognition, machine learning, and voice bots. Given the limited availability of reliable external APIs, the decision was to utilize a JSON file for custom data input. To develop the content, key questions were outlined and responses were meticulously researched for accuracy. Ethika was then built on Replit, using Python for its simplicity. The chatbot's responses are guided by 'if-else' statements, enabling it to retrieve answers from the JSON file or prompt users to provide new information if no match is found. This leads to the central question of the paper: How can chatbots allow users to manage their mental health by providing digital phenotyping data?

```
Hello! I am Ethika, here to help analyze your digital data. What is your average screen time per day? (Please provide the number of minutes without using the word "minutes" in your answer.) Disclaimer: I am not a medical professional. Please do not share any sensitive information.  
You: 120  
Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is exactly the recommended amount (2 hours or less not counting work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?
```

Figure 6: Ethika greets the user and asks for their average daily screen time in minutes. The user responds with 120 minutes, which is within the recommended range so Ethika applauds them. Ethika then inquires whether the user uses their device in the morning or before bed.

```
Hello! I am Ethika, here to help analyze your digital data. What is your average screen time per day? (Please provide the number of minutes without using the word "minutes" in your answer.) Disclaimer: I am not a medical professional. Please do not share any sensitive information.  
You: 113  
Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is less than the recommended amount (2 hours or less not counting work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?
```

Figure 7: Ethika greets the user and asks for their average daily screen time in minutes. The user replies with 113 minutes, which is below the recommended amount so Ethika praises them. Ethika then inquires whether the user uses their device in the morning or before bed.

Adhering to the recommended screen time limit of 2 hours or less per day, excluding work-related usage, is a commendable step towards maintaining overall well-being. This approach helps mitigate the potential negative effects of excessive screen exposure, such as stress and decreased productivity. Effective management of screen time can significantly enhance both mental clarity and physical health. According to Figures 6 and 7, continuing to monitor and adjust screen usage fosters a more balanced lifestyle and improves daily routines. Ethika supports this approach, recognizing that such mindful management contributes to a healthier, more productive daily routine.

```
Hello! I am Ethika, here to help analyze your digital data. What is your average screen time per day? (Please provide the number of minutes without using the word "minutes" in your answer.) Disclaimer: I am not a medical professional. Please do not share any sensitive information.  
You: 357  
Ethika: Your screen time is higher than the recommended amount by the FDA (2 hours or less not counting work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?
```

Figure 8: Ethika greets the user and asks for their average daily screen time in minutes. The user reports 357 minutes, which exceeds the recommended amount. Ethika then inquires whether the user uses their device in the morning or before bed.

As detailed in Figure 8, the screen time currently exceeds the FDA's recommended limit of 2 hours per day, not including work-related usage. Ethika, understanding its programming, recognizes this issue and advises the user to reduce their screen time. This guideline is intended to help manage and reduce the negative effects associated with excessive screen exposure, which can impact both physical and mental health. High screen time has been linked to various issues, such as decreased productivity, increased stress, and poor sleep quality. Adjusting screen habits to align more closely with these recommendations can be beneficial. Implementing strategies like setting limits on recreational screen use and taking regular breaks can contribute

to improved well-being. Adhering to these guidelines can enhance productivity, mental health, and overall quality of life.

```
Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is less than the recommended amount (2 hours or less not counting work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?  
You: yes  
Ethika: Avoid using screens in the morning because it disrupts productivity and in the nighttime as the blue rays emitted from your device can reduce the sleep hormone melatonin, disrupting your sleep cycle as well as leaving you tired in the morning. Is your most used app gaming, social media, entertainment or messaging? (please answer using the words 'gaming', 'social media' or 'messaging')
```

Figure 9: Ethika advises users on the adverse mental health effects of using their device immediately upon waking or just before sleeping, highlighting these habits as detrimental to overall well-being.

```
Ethika: Your screen time is higher than the recommended amount by the FDA (2 hours or less not counting work hours). Do you use your device in the first hour when you wake up in the morning/the hour before you go to bed?  
You: no  
Ethika: Great job! Not looking at a screen in the first hour of the morning boosts mood and productivity for the rest of the day while not looking at a screen an hour before bedtime leads to good, sound sleep which boosts your energy for the next day! Is your most used app gaming, social media, entertainment or messaging? (please answer using the words 'gaming', 'social media' or 'messaging')
```

Figure 10: Upon discovering that the user does not use their device immediately upon waking or before going to sleep, Ethika commends them and explains the mental health benefits of maintaining this healthy routine.

According to Figures 9 and 10, Ethika highlights the importance of managing screen time to boost productivity and improve sleep quality. Using screens in the morning can disrupt your ability to start the day effectively, while nighttime screen use is particularly problematic. The blue light emitted from devices interferes with melatonin production which regulates your sleep cycle. Disruption in melatonin levels can lead to poor sleep quality, making you feel tired and groggy the next morning. To enhance both productivity and sleep, it's beneficial to limit screen time, especially in the hours before bed. This approach supports better sleep hygiene and overall well-being.

```
Ethika: Avoid using screens in the morning because it disrupts productivity and in the nighttime as the blue rays emitted from your device can reduce the sleep hormone melatonin, disrupting your sleep cycle as well as leaving you tired in the morning. Is your most used app gaming, social media, entertainment or messaging? (please answer using the words 'gaming', 'social media' or 'messaging')  
You: social media  
Ethika: Excessive social media use can lead to increased levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, while also encouraging pressures to compete for popularity. You can decrease the amount of time you spend on social media by setting a time limit on your device, try to plan hangouts with friends/family or if it is truly difficult for you to get away from social media, try to find a hobby that you enjoy and do not have to use your phone. Examples of hobbies include reading, writing, crocheting, knitting, some type of sport, art or even just taking a simple walk outside.
```

Figure 11: When the user types “social media,” Ethika addresses the negative effects of excessive social media use. She also suggests hobbies and activities that are more mentally and physically beneficial.

Ethika highlights that excessive social media use can lead to heightened levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, as well as foster unhealthy competition for popularity as seen in Figure 11. To combat these issues, Ethika suggests setting a time limit on your device to manage social media use more effectively. Planning real-life interactions with friends and family can also help reduce screen time. If disconnecting from social media proves particularly challenging, finding hobbies that don't involve your phone may be beneficial. Engaging in reading, writing, crocheting, knitting, participating in sports, or creating art can offer fulfilling alternatives. Even a simple walk outside can provide a refreshing break from digital pressures and contribute positively to your mental well-being.

```
Ethika: Great job! Not looking at a screen in the first hour of the morning boosts mood and productivity for the rest of the day while not looking at a screen an hour before bedtime leads to good, sound sleep which boosts your energy for the next day! Is your most used app gaming, social media, entertainment or messaging? (please answer using the words 'gaming', 'social media' or 'messaging')
You: messaging
Ethika: Excessive messaging can lead to sleep disturbances, poor posture, and physical pain in the hands, neck, and eyes, while also contributing to anxiety and depression. To counter these effects, consider reducing screen time and engaging in activities like physical exercise, reading, or creative arts. Incorporating hobbies such as music, outdoor activities, or mindfulness practices can improve well-being and provide a healthy balance.
```

Figure 12: When the user types "messaging," Ethika outlines the negative effects of excessive messaging and provides tips on how to reduce screen time and give their eyes a break.

Referring to Figure 12, Ethika asks if the most frequently used app is for gaming, social media, entertainment, or messaging. Upon responding to "messaging," Ethika explains that excessive messaging can cause issues, including sleep disturbances, poor posture, and physical discomfort in the hands, neck, and eyes. Furthermore, it can contribute to heightened anxiety and depression. To counteract these negative effects, Ethika recommends limiting screen time and engaging in many activities such as physical exercise, reading, or creative arts. By incorporating hobbies like playing music, participating in outdoor activities, or practicing mindfulness, you can significantly improve your overall well-being and achieve a healthier, more balanced lifestyle.

```
Ethika: Avoid using screens in the morning because it disrupts productivity and in the nighttime as the blue rays emitted from your device can reduce the sleep hormone melatonin, disrupting your sleep cycle as well as leaving you tired in the morning. Is your most used app gaming, social media, entertainment or messaging? (please answer using the words 'gaming', 'social media' or 'messaging')
You: gaming
Ethika: Too much video game use (especially if they are violent) can lead to problems such as decreased physical activity, laziness, lack of productivity, disrupted sleep patterns, and potential social isolation. Set specific limits on your gaming sessions and explore alternatives like creating board game versions, hanging out with friends/family, exploring new hobbies that get you moving, reading books about your video game world or trying a new sport.
```

Figure 13: When the user types "gaming," Ethika highlights the risks of excessive gaming and provides tips for reducing screen time and taking breaks.

In Figure 13, Ethika elaborates on the adverse effects of excessive video game usage, particularly violent games, which include reduced physical activity, increased laziness, diminished productivity, disrupted sleep patterns, and potentially social isolation. To mitigate these issues, Ethika recommends establishing specific limits on gaming sessions and exploring

alternative activities such as creating board game adaptations, socializing with friends and family, engaging in new physical hobbies, reading literature related to video game worlds, or participating in new sports.

DISCUSSION

The research question investigated in this paper is "How can chatbots allow users to manage their mental health by providing digital phenotyping data?" Digital phenotyping offers a new perspective on mental health by making it more personalized and subjective, harnessing 21st-century technologies to advance preventive and effective medicine (Oudin et al. 2023). Using Ethika in this paper, the chatbot's responses—based on a user's screen time and most frequently used apps, which together form their digital phenotype—can assist users in managing healthy screen times. This approach can improve mental health, as Ethika analyzed the user's data and specifically provided advice to improve their digital habits. Therefore, the hypothesis is proven true through this paper.

Based on Figures 6, 7, and 8, Ethika begins by introducing herself and then asks the question, "What is your average screen time per day?" In recent years, there has been a significant rise in the use of display screen equipment (DSE) during people's leisure time (Li et al. 2022). Extremely high levels of screen time can detrimentally affect mental health, leading to more sedentary lifestyles where people are less active and physically fit. This can lead to lagged development, psychosocial symptoms, obesity, sleep disorders, and cardiovascular disease (Li et al. 2022). This is why Ethika has a set threshold in her code that states any screen time above 120 minutes (2 hours) is not healthy. In Figure 8, the user reports 357 minutes of screen time, far exceeding the recommended two-hour limit. A November 2021 JAMA Pediatrics study found that 12 to 13-year-olds now average 7.7 hours of screen time per day, nearly double the pre-pandemic 3.8 hours, while the recommended limit remains two hours (Johnson 2022). Meanwhile, in Figures 6 and 7, the screentime is 120 minutes and 113 minutes which is either equivalent or below the recommended time. Ethika commends the users for their healthy screen time limit and then moves to the next question.

After the user inputs their screen time and receives feedback, Ethika will ask whether they use their phone in the morning or at the end of the day. Based on their answer, Ethika will either compliment the user for avoiding phone use during the first hour or provide advice to improve their habits if they use their phone during that time. Using smartphones in the morning can disrupt brain wave patterns, shifting from a relaxed state to a more agitated one, which might impact mental health and well-being by inducing stress (Sharma 2023). This can decrease an individual's productivity and lower their mood, as illustrated in Figures 9 and 10, which show the negative effects of phone use during the first hour of the morning. Along with this, Ethika also explains the harmful side effects of using your phone right before bedtime. Research shows that these devices can interfere with sleep by lowering melatonin levels, a hormone that helps induce tiredness (Pacheco & Truong 2023). This disruption leads to heightened alertness through neurophysiologic stimulation, making it harder to relax and fall asleep (Pacheco & Truong 2023). Additionally, the blue light emitted from devices can affect the rapid eye movement (REM) stage of sleep. REM sleep is crucial for vivid dreaming, emotional processing, memory consolidation, brain development, and preparing for the next day (Summer & Singh 2024).

Ethika then leads the user to the next question: "Is your most used app gaming, social media, or messaging?" If the user responds with social media, Ethika will explain the potential harm to mental well-being associated with excessive social media use and offer suggestions for alternative activities to reduce reliance on these platforms, as shown in Figure 11. Social media can lead to addiction by triggering dopamine release with each interaction, a phenomenon that

social media companies exploit to keep users engaged and drive up their revenue (Sharma 2023). Young adults who spend significant time on social media are notably more likely to display signs of depression (Withington & Punch 2019). This extensive use often results in a decrease in perceived emotional support, an increase in the fear of missing out (FOMO), and a drop in self-esteem. The constant comparison to others' seemingly perfect lives can also lead to social comparison and peer envy, which are major contributors to depressive symptoms (Withington & Punch 2019). Ethika's guidance aims to help users understand these impacts and find healthier ways to engage in entertainment and communication, ultimately promoting better mental health.

When an individual selects messaging, Ethika will inform them about the negative consequences of excessive texting, emphasizing the importance of balancing screen time with face-to-face interactions or phone calls. She will also suggest strategies for reducing screen time by exploring new hobbies or interests, as illustrated in Figure 12. Excessive texting can lead to psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem, as well as physical health problems (Kori 2024). Additionally, frequent texting may be indicative of underlying mental health struggles (Kori 2024). By encouraging users to engage in offline activities and foster real-world connections, Ethika aims to help them minimize these risks and promote overall well-being.

Based on Figure 13, if the user responds with gaming as their most used app, Ethika will answer with the potential negative effects of gaming, the criticality of controlling the time you spend gaming, and ways to stay active to avoid addiction. Video game obsession is a serious issue and is classified as an Internet gaming disorder (IGD), which is closely linked to problems with motivational control and is often compared to gambling addiction (Mohammad et al. 2023). Specifically, violent games have an amplified impact on these effects, especially on children as they easily adopt behaviors they observe. A study found that early exposure to violent video games such as World of Warcraft, Grand Theft Auto, Call of Duty, Valorant, and Fortnite is associated with increased aggressive behavior and thinking in children. This exposure can negatively impact emotional and psychological well-being, leading to higher temper, nightmares, sleep issues, and poor academic performance. (Harvard Health 2010).

After Ethika responds with the negative effects of the different kinds of apps (social media, gaming, messaging), she recommends recreational activities as alternatives to reduce screen time. These include finding and exploring new hobbies such as reading, writing, sports, or walking outside. Ethika recommends sports and exercise because regular physical activity to build cardiovascular endurance, and strength training to build lean muscle mass and burn fat is crucial to living a long, healthy life. This can prevent chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, hypertension, obesity, depression, and osteoporosis (Warburton et al. 2006). Additionally, other methods of keeping the mind occupied include intellectual stimulation activities such as reading and writing. Although some people do not find reading entertaining, the potential benefits will outweigh this. Reading just 6 minutes can enhance sleep quality, alleviate stress, boost mental sharpness, strengthen neural connections, and even reduce heart rate and blood pressure (Martinez 2020).

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Currently, Ethika operates without artificial intelligence, relying instead on predefined responses and basic algorithms to interact with users. While this approach provides a functional tool for managing screen time and answering general queries, it lacks advanced capabilities such as personalized interactions and adaptive learning. However, with technological advancements and contributions from skilled developers, Ethika is envisioned to integrate sophisticated techniques.

This enhancement could enable the chatbot to analyze complex patterns in user behavior, offer more nuanced and personalized mental health support, and adapt dynamically to individual needs. By incorporating AI, Ethika could transform from a basic information tool into an even more intelligent and responsive healthcare assistant, significantly advancing its role in mental health management and intervention.

Another significant challenge is the relatively sparse research on chatbot applications in mental health, which limits understanding and integration into healthcare. The lack of extensive studies means many potential benefits, such as early diagnosis, personalized treatment plans, and ongoing patient support, remain unexplored. This research gap restricts AI's potential in enhancing mental health care. However, targeted research efforts could uncover deeper insights and lead to the development of innovative tools tailored to mental health challenges, ultimately advancing the field and improving patient outcomes.

Ethika's inability to replace medical professionals further impacts the accuracy and reliability of the health information it provides. Without the expertise of qualified healthcare providers, there is a risk of publicizing inaccurate or outdated medical advice, which could lead to misinformation or gaps in essential knowledge. To address this issue, involving medical professionals in the continuous review and validation of Ethika's content is crucial. Their oversight would ensure the platform delivers accurate, up-to-date health information, enhancing its effectiveness and reliability.

Woebot, a mental health app, is an example of integrating mental health support with health plans, healthcare systems, and employers. It focuses on replacing negative self-critique with self-compassion, clarifying personal values, retraining positive thinking, and understanding emotions. Similarly, Ethika could benefit from incorporating advanced sentiment analysis and emotional recognition technologies. By leveraging deep learning techniques, Ethika could better understand user emotions and offer more empathetic and contextually appropriate responses, improving support for users in complex emotional states and enhancing its effectiveness in managing digital habits.

To further enhance Ethika's effectiveness, several improvements are needed. Integrating data from wearable devices and health apps would provide a comprehensive view of a user's well-being by tracking physiological indicators such as sleep patterns and stress levels. Adding collaborative features could enable users to share progress with trusted individuals or health professionals, fostering a supportive community. Personalized intervention plans, incorporating gaming and interactive elements, could boost engagement and adherence. Expanding accessibility by offering multiple languages and cultural adaptations would make Ethika beneficial to a broader, more diverse audience.

IMPLICATIONS

Researching how chatbots can facilitate mental health management through digital phenotyping data is essential due to the growing need for innovative, accessible, and effective mental health solutions. Chatbots, equipped with sophisticated algorithms and natural language processing capabilities, can interact with users to gather extensive data on their emotional states, behavioral patterns, and overall well-being. This digital phenotyping data—collected through routine interactions—can be analyzed to provide real-time insights into a user's mental health. By identifying trends and detecting anomalies in user behavior and mood, these chatbots can help in early diagnosis and intervention for mental health conditions such as anxiety, depression, and stress. This capability to monitor and assess mental health in real-time offers a significant advantage over traditional methods, which rely on periodic assessments and self-reported data.

Furthermore, the research into chatbots for mental health management addresses accessibility. Many individuals face barriers to traditional mental health care, including geographical limitations, financial constraints, and stigma. Chatbots have the potential to bridge these gaps by providing continuous, anonymous support that can be accessed from anywhere at any time. By exploring how these chatbots use digital phenotyping data, researchers can evaluate their effectiveness in delivering personalized care, tailoring interventions to individual needs, and ensuring that these tools are reliable and ethical. This research is vital for understanding how AI-driven solutions can complement or enhance existing mental health services, ultimately leading to more inclusive and adaptive approaches to mental health care.

CONCLUSION

In essence, chatbots and digital phenotyping in mental health care hold transformative potential, particularly through platforms like Ethika. Our findings demonstrate that Ethika, utilizing digital data analysis, can provide valuable insights into users' mental well-being, offering personalized recommendations and early intervention strategies without direct input from medical professionals. This approach makes mental health support more accessible to the world, especially in regions lacking adequate resources or for individuals hesitant to seek therapy due to cultural, religious, or societal beliefs. As demonstrated, digital phenotyping techniques allow Ethika to assess mental health through patterns in screen time, app usage, and other digital interactions. By analyzing these patterns, Ethika can deliver advice that helps users manage their mental health proactively. This is particularly crucial in a post-pandemic world where the demand for mental health services has surged, and traditional methods such as going to a psychiatrist or therapist alone may not suffice. Despite its potential, chatbots in mental health care must be approached carefully. Ensuring data privacy, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining the accuracy of chatbot recommendations are essential to mitigate risks and maintain user trust. Ethika, while valuable as a supplementary tool, should not replace professional medical advice but rather complement existing mental health resources.

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Appendix A

```

import json
from difflib import get_close_matches

def load_knowledge_base(file_path: str) -> dict:
    with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
        data: dict = json.load(file)
    return data

def save_knowledge_base(file_path: str, data: dict):
    with open(file_path, 'w') as file:
        json.dump(data, file, indent=2)

def find_best_match(user_question: str, questions: list[str]) -
> str | None:
    matches: list = get_close_matches(user_question, questions,
n=1, cutoff=0.6)
    return matches[0] if matches else None

def get_answer_for_question(question: str, knowledge_base:
dict) -> str | None:
    for q in knowledge_base["questions"]:
        if q["question"] == question:
            return q["answer"]
    return None

def chat_bot():
    knowledge_base_file = 'knowledge_base.json'
    knowledge_base: dict =
load_knowledge_base(knowledge_base_file)

    print('Hello! I am Ethika, here to help analyze your
digital data. '
        'What is your average screen time per day? (Please
provide '
        'the number of minutes without using the word
"minutes" in your '
        'answer.) Disclaimer: I am not a medical
professional. Please do not '
        'share any sensitive information.')

    threshold = 120

```

```

while True:
    user_input: str = input('You: ')

    if user_input.lower() in ['quit', 'bye', 'exit']:
        break

    try:
        user_number = float(user_input)
        if user_number > threshold:
            print('Ethika: Your screen time is higher than
                '
                'the recommended amount by the FDA (2
hours '
                'or less not counting work hours). Do you
use '
                'your device in the first hour when you
wake '
                'up in the morning/the hour before you go
to bed?')
        elif user_number == threshold:
            print('Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is
                '
                'the recommended amount (2 hours or less
not counting '
                'work hours). Do you use your device in
the first hour '
                'when you wake up in the morning/the hour
before you go to bed?')
        else:
            print('Ethika: Great job! Your screen time is
                '
                'recommended amount (2 hours or less not
counting work hours). '
                'Do you use your device in the first hour
when you wake up in '
                'the morning/the hour before you go to
bed?')

    except ValueError:
        best_match: str | None =
find_best_match(user_input, [q["question"] for q in

```

```
knowledge_base["questions"]])

    if best_match:
        answer: str | None =
get_answer_for_question(best_match, knowledge_base)
        print(f'Ethika: {answer}')
    else:
        print("Ethika: I don't have an answer for that
question. Can you teach me?")
        new_answer: str = input('Type the answer or
"skip" to skip: ')

        if new_answer.lower() != 'skip':

knowledge_base["questions"].append({"question": user_input,
"answer": new_answer})
        save_knowledge_base(knowledge_base_file,
knowledge_base)
        print('Ethika: Thank you for teaching me!')
    else:
        print('Ethika: Okay, no problem.')

    print("Ethika: I hope your mental health will improve! Feel
free to check in again! Goodbye!")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    chat_bot()
```